

HealthyFoodAfrica Food System Lab Bahir Dar

Theme: Improving nutrition by strengthening
production and consumption of healthy diet around
Bahir Dar

Book of Abstracts

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Message Form FSL BD- Focal Person

Bahir Dar University (BDU) has been implementing the EU Horizon 2020-supported project “Improving nutrition in Africa by strengthening the diversity, sustainability, resilience, and connectivity of food systems” in short, “HealthyFoodAfrica” in the urban and peri-urban areas of Bahir Dar city. In an effort of co-creating research agendas, we collected baseline information, identified food system bottlenecks, and piloted different action research in close collaboration with stakeholders. The pilot actions focused on the production, postharvest handling, distribution, marketing, and utilization of nutrition foods such as pulses, vegetables, fruits, and fish. The project has been implemented for the last four years, whereby four academic staff of BDU are involved along with six PhD and nine MSc students.

HealthyFoodAfrica-Food System Lab Bahir Dar organized a review and dissemination workshop to evaluate the merits of the different scientific outcomes with the goal of disseminating the information to end-users, namely producers, traders, and nutrition experts. The implications of the research outcomes are also expected to be communicated to relevant decision-makers. This Book of Abstracts entails 25 abstracts related to different commodities, food governance, and nutrition. Fifteen of them were presented in the two-day’ workshop. Over 70 individuals from different sector offices, cooperatives, experts, academicians, and students participated. A prominent scientist gave an inspiring keynote speech on the theme: Food System for Sustainable Nutrition Security and Health.

Besides the scientific outputs (publication of five papers and submission of another four papers in peer-reviewed international journals), four field days were organized, two guidelines (nutrition education material and haricot bean production) have been developed, and two poster presentations in international conferences were held. The nutrition education material is expected to improve maternal and child nutrition by transforming consumption patterns towards sustainable, healthy diets.

The workshop deliberations recommended the development of five additional production guidelines and several policy briefs. Based on the guidelines, another workshop is planned to be organized with farmers and development agents in December 2024. The FSL lab Bahir Dar is also committed to publishing an additional of at least five scientific papers. Based on feedback from workshop participants, it was argued that the project is quite successful.

The Rise and Fall of Onion Production and Multiple Constraints on Pre-Harvest and Post-Harvest Management Issues on the Supply Chain in Northwest Ethiopia

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Abstract

Food and nutrition security is not only addressed by increasing production alone. It should also be ensured by reducing food loss. Onion has a great contribution to both economic and health issues; however, its production and productivity in the country is low. Thus, the study was initiated to identify multiple constraints on onion production and post-harvest handling practices and to determine the extent of post-harvest loss on the supply chain in northwestern Ethiopia. The survey was conducted on production, marketing, and consumption at farm, wholesale, retailer, and consumer's level. The multistage sampling technique was employed for selecting the participants. The collected data revealed that sex, age, educational level, production experience, land covered by onion, and household size had a significant influence on onion production. Besides, sex, age, education level, active household size, selling experience, amount purchased, and storage duration showed a significant association with onion production and post-harvest loss. Major onion production and post-harvest loss constraints were: high perishability, nature of the crop, market, linkage problem and low market price, lack of awareness of using post-harvest technologies, absence of better storable varieties, shortage of fertilizer access, disease and insect pests. The whole purchased produce never reached the consumer's hands. The total post-harvest loss of onion at the farmer, wholesale, retail, and consumer level was found to be 29.775%, of which the higher proportion of the losses (35.5%) was observed at the farmer's level. Based on the findings, onion producers were challenged by untimely and inadequate supplies, high cost of major production inputs and high post-harvest loss. Therefore, producers and handlers in each supply chain need to be trained on affordable and applicable post-harvest technologies. In addition, continuous capacity-building, improved infrastructure, and input access on the supply chain should be designed and implemented to improve better crop management and post-harvest handling practices. Moreover, marketing cooperatives working on onion post-harvest handling and marketing systems should be functional to absorb surplus production and ensure continuous supply to the market. Thus, meaningful interventions in the development and implementation of policy on onion sustainable production, handling practices, and supply should be designed.

Keywords: Onion, Supply chain, Raise, Fall, Constraint, Pre-harvest, post-harvest loss

Strategic Mapping of Onion Supply Chains: A Comprehensive Analysis of Production and Post-Harvest Processes in Northwest Ethiopia

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Abstract

Onions is a significant vegetable crop in Ethiopia, serving as a source of income for smallholder farmers. However, various challenges in the production and post-harvest handling processes impede a consistent supply and marketing of the crop. This study focused on a comprehensive analysis of the onion supply chain- (ranging from production to post-harvest handling) to address the existing production and marketing processes. This research was undertaken to map the onion supply chain from farmers to consumers for establishing an improved marketing system in northwest Ethiopia. The study area covered three onion-producing districts of Amhara Region. Data collection instruments include interviews, observations, and a structured questionnaire. Sampling employed a multistage technique. Analysis used descriptive statistics and food system analysis to map the supply chain and estimate marketing margins. The results revealed that post-harvest loss in onion production became a major obstacle in the farming sector. The results further identified six alternative channels for onion marketing where different actors involved throughout the supply chain. Key stakeholders include farmers, local collectors, brokers, transporters, wholesalers, retailers, and consumers. Packaging and sorting activities were implemented at different supply chain stages to minimize post-harvest losses. Farm-level activities including curing, sorting, grading, and ventilating were crucial for reducing losses. The perishable nature of onion bulbs and the existing production and handling challenges could exacerbate post-harvest losses. Efforts to address this challenge requires a comprehensive approach that integrates interventions across the value chain (from improved cultivars and storage infrastructure to enhanced market access strategies). Hence, stakeholders and governmental organizations are urged to promote onion value-addition technologies, including establishment of processing industries through promoting collaborative efforts across the onion supply chain for ensuring sustainable benefits for producers and traders.

Keywords: Onion supply chain; Mapping, Market channel, Smallholder farmers, Production challenges, Market prices, post-harvest handling, post-harvest losses

Enhancing Bulb Yield through Nitrogen Fertilization and the Use of Hybrid Onion (*Allium cepa*) Varieties in Northwest Ethiopia

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Abstract

Onions are among the most important cash crops in developing countries, including Ethiopia. However, its production and productivity are very low, which is associated with inappropriate use of fertilizer and having low-yielding varieties. Therefore, the present study was conducted to see the effects of nitrogen fertilizer rate on the growth, yield, and quality of hybrid onion varieties in northwest Ethiopia. Experiment was conducted in three locations such as Koga, Woreta, and Woramit during the 2021/2022 cropping season under irrigated conditions. The treatments consisted of three hybrid onion varieties (Russet, Jambar, Red Coach) and one open-pollinated onion variety (Bombay Red) and four nitrogen rates (0, 41, 82, and 123 kg ha⁻¹), which were layout in a randomized complete block design in a factorial arrangement of 4*4 in three replications. The results of the study showed that onion growth, yield and quality were influenced by the main effects of nitrogen fertilizer rate and onion variety across all locations. Russet and Jambar varieties recorded the highest marketable yield of 26.50 t ha⁻¹ and 24.57 t ha⁻¹ combined over the three locations, respectively. Similarly, Onion plants supplied with 82 kg ha⁻¹ nitrogen recorded the highest marketable bulb yield of 26.77 t ha⁻¹ combined over the three locations. Application of N greater than 82 kg ha⁻¹ leads to reduction of bulb yield and prolonging of the maturity across the three locations. Furthermore, Jambar and Russet hybrid varieties supplied with 82 kg N ha⁻¹ nitrogen recorded the highest net benefits. The use of Jambar and Russet varieties and the application of 82 kg ha⁻¹ nitrogen can be, therefore, recommended for the production of onion at North Mecha, Fogera, and Bahir Dar Zuria districts and areas with similar agro-ecology. It is also recommended consideration of other hybrid onion varieties and optimization of agronomic practices such as spacing and phosphorus fertilizer in future research works.

Keywords: Onion; Hybrid varieties; Nitrogen fertilizer, Growth; Yield, Quality, Net benefit

Influence of Variety and Plant Density on the Growth, Yield of the Bulb and Quality Traits of Onion (*Allium cepa*)

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Abstract

Optimization of the agronomic practices including plant population has been essential for enhancing the productivity of onion. This study was, therefore, meant to investigate impacts of three planting densities (222,222, 333,333, 666,666 plants ha⁻¹) and three hybrid (Russet, Jamber, Red Coach) and one open pollinated (Bombay Red) of onion varieties on growth and yield of onion in three locations, namely Koga Irrigation Scheme, Woramit and Woreta. The study was conducted during the 2021/2022 irrigation season. Treatments were conducted in a Randomized Complete Block Design with three replications. The results of the study showed that the growth and yield of onion were influenced by plant density and onion varieties across the three locations. Russet and Jambar varieties of onion consistently exhibited the highest values for bulb diameter, average bulb weight, harvest index, firmness, total bulb yield and marketable bulb yield in all locations. The highest marketable bulb yields of 28.09 t ha⁻¹ and 26.61 t ha⁻¹ were recorded from Russet and Jambar varieties of onion, respectively. Marketable bulb yield was positively correlated with plant height, bulb weight, and bulb diameter of onion. Planting the onion varieties at higher plant population (666,666 plants ha⁻¹) with the spacing of 5 cm x 20 cm x 40 cm between plants, row and double row, respectively also recorded the highest marketable bulb yield (28.42 t ha⁻¹). Therefore, planting Russet and Jambar hybrid onion varieties along with higher plant population (5 cm between plants x 20 cm between rows x 40 cm between row spacing) is recommended for enhancing the productivity of onion in the study area and areas with similar agro-ecology. Testing these and other hybrid onion varieties with higher levels of plant population is also recommended in future research works.

Keywords: Hybrid onion variety; Marketable bulb yield; Plant density; Russet variety

Effects of Hybrid Variety, Nitrogen Fertilizer, and Packaging Materials on Post-Harvest Quality of Onion in Northwest Ethiopia

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Abstract

Seasonality of production and perishable nature of the onions are leading to the abundance and scarcity of the crop in the market supply. On the other hand, the storage potential, quality and shelf life of onions are influenced by onion varieties, fertilizer application, growing and storage conditions. Therefore, the study aims to examine the influence of packaging materials (shelf, sack floor), variety (Russet, Jamber, Red Coach, Bombay Red) and nitrogen fertilizer rate (0, 41, 82, and 123 kg ha⁻¹) agronomic practices on the post-harvest quality and shelf of onion grown in different environments. The treatments were organized in a factorial arrangement in a randomized complete block design (RCBD) with three replications. The results indicated that post-harvest quality (attributes of onion) particularly the shelf life of onion was greatly influenced by onion varieties, packaging materials and nitrogen fertilization in three locations. The present results also confirmed that onion bulbs could be stored for one month with proper handling, regardless of packaging materials. Bulbs of Jambar and Russet varieties produced by the application of 82 kg/ha N and storage on shelves recorded the longest days to begin sprouting and had the lowest decay percentage and the highest percentage of marketable bulb yield. The bulbs were also relatively firm and recorded the lowest weight loss. The highest storage loss (higher percentage of sprouting, decay, weight loss, and lower marketable bulbs) was observed from Bombay Red variety followed by Red Coach while the longer shelf life was seen on bulbs of Jambar and Russet varieties stored on shelves. According to the present study results, varietal selection, proper storage practices, and nutrient management could be essential for maintaining the quality, extending the shelf life and reducing the post-harvest losses of onion so as to ensure sustainable onion supply in the market. Besides, producing of Russet and Jambar varieties and storing their bulbs on shelves constructed from locally available materials could help reducing post-harvest losses of onion.

Keywords; Onion; Post-harvest, Shelf life; Storage period, packaging material

Food System Lab Bahir Dar

Influences of Pre-harvest Treatments on Post-harvest Quality and Shelf life of *Allium cepa* L Onion () Varieties in Bahir Dar District, Amhara Region

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Abstract

Onion is the most important and widely cultivated bulb vegetable in Ethiopia. However, high post-harvest loss during storage is one of the main challenges of the onion production. The present study was, therefore, conducted to investigate effects of selected pre-harvest treatments on shelf life and post-harvest quality of onion varieties in diffused light storage structure. The bulbs of three hybrid (Red coach, Russet, Jambar) and one open-pollinated (Bombay red) varieties produced in Woramit Research Site ARARI during the 2023 irrigation season using uniform and standard agronomic practices were used. The pre-harvest treatments were toppling at 70% neck fall with and without irrigation, toppling at 90% neck fall, and harvesting at 70% neck fall without toppling. Moreover, the post-harvest parameters of bulbs were collected at 0th, 4th, 8th and 12th week of storage. Accordingly, the treatments were arranged with 4*4*4 factorial combinations in RCBD with three replications in the storage experiment. Based on the treatment setup, bulbs were stored in DLS in Zenzelema campus of Bahir Dar University for three months. Data on post-harvest quality parameters were collected and analyzed using mixed model combined analysis SAS (version 9.4) software where pre-harvest treatment and variety were considered as fixed variables while storage duration was considered as random variable. The results of combined analysis of variance revealed that variety, pre-harvest treatment and storage duration influenced most of the tested parameters of onion in the storage. Similarly, the interaction of variety and pre-harvest treatments influenced decay percentage (P<0.001), bulb firmness (P<0.001), total soluble solid of onion bulbs (P<0.0001) and marketable bulbs yield (P<0.001) throughout the storage duration. The varieties Jambar and Russet and the practice of toppling at 90% maturity recorded the lowest sprouting and weight loss percentage and the highest proportion of marketable bulbs and highest bulb firmness in the storage. On the other hand, Bombay red variety, toppled at 70% maturity followed by irrigation recorded the highest sprouting, decay percentage, bulb weight loss and the lowest bulb firmness. Producing Jambar and Russet varieties and practicing toppling at 90% maturity could maintain the quality and reduce post-harvest losses of onion bulbs in the storage. As the study is limited to single location and season, it is recommended to repeat the study in multiplications and seasons.

Keywords: Onion, Hybrid varieties, Shelf life, Toppling, Yield

Growth and Yield Performance of Hybrid Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculuntem* Mill) Varieties under High Tunnel Production System During Rainy Season at Koga Irrigation Scheme, Northwest Ethiopia

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Abstract

Tomato production in Ethiopia is mostly practiced during the off season, using irrigation, since production of Tomato in the rainy season is affected by high incidence of fungal diseases. The market supply of tomatoes during the rainy season is, therefore, minimal that drives its price to unaffordable level. Recently, however, smallholder farmers are using Polyhouse technology that protects tomatoes from rain and thus reduces the incidence of diseases especially the late blight. Therefore, a field experiment was conducted at Koga Irrigation Scheme to evaluate the growth and yield performance of hybrid tomato varieties under high tunnel production system during the rainy season. Accordingly, three hybrid tomato varieties (Galilea, Gabbi and Galilea-39) were grown under polyhouse during the 2022 rainy season in four replications at Koga Irrigation Scheme, which were arranged in Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD). Data on growth, phenology, yield and quality parameters of tomato were collected and analyzed using the SAS-9.4 software. The results showed significant differences among the three hybrid tomato varieties for most of the growth parameters and yield components in each location. Gabbi variety recorded the tallest plant height (174.84-180.54 cm), more number of primary branches (8.91-9.72) and secondary branches (17.30-19.32), the highest number of flower cluster (29.75-34.45), flower per cluster (6.86-7.36), fruit per cluster (5.29-6.01), fruit set percentage (72.64-84.10%), marketable yield (90.75-103.07t/ha) and total yield (92.20-104.31 t/ha) in all locations except in Kudmi. Combined over locations Gabbi variety recorded the tallest plant height (174.63 cm), more number of primary branches (8.60) and secondary branches (17.61), the highest number of flower clusters per plant (29.17), number of flowers (6.68) and number of fruits per cluster (5.00), the longest fruit length (6.83cm), the highest marketable yield (89.11 t/ha) and total fruit yield (90.32 t/ha). The financial feasibility study of high tunnel production system of tomatoes during the rainy season also showed a positive net present value (4,135.27ETB per 140 m² area) a benefit to cost ratio of 1.25 and an internal rate of return of 24% at 18% interest rate. The production of tomato in high tunnel production system during the rainy season is, therefore, highly feasible and profitable where the variety Gabbi could be used at Koga Irrigation Scheme and similar agro-ecology. Further research works on fertilizer optimization and disease and insect pest management options are also suggested.

Keywords: Financial feasibility, Gabbi variety, Fruit set percentage

Response of Hybrid Tomato Variety to Nitrogen and Phosphorous Fertilizer Rates in High Tunnel Production System During the Rainy Season in Koga Irrigation Scheme, Amhara Region, Ethiopia

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Abstract

Tomato is the most popular and widely cultivated vegetable crop worldwide for its rich source of micronutrients and minerals. Although tomato production is mainly confined to the dry season, nowadays smallholder farmers in Ethiopia are producing tomato during the rainy season under high tunnel production system. However, there is no recommended fertilizer rate for high tunnel production of tomatoes. Cognizant of this, an experiment was conducted during 2023 main cropping season at Koga Irrigation scheme of North Mecha district to investigate effects of N and P fertilizers application on growth, yield and quality of tomato under high tunnel production system. The treatment consisted of a combination of four levels of N (0, 160, 320 and 480 kg ha⁻¹) and four levels of P (0, 40, 80 and 120 kg ha⁻¹) fertilizers. The experiment was organized in a factorial arrangement with RCBD and three replications. Hybrid Galilia tomato variety was used as test crop. Data on phenology, growth, yield and physico-chemical quality attributes of tomato were collected and analyzed using SAS V.9.0. Results from the analysis of variance revealed that all traits of tomatoes were significantly influenced by the main effects and interaction effect of nitrogen and phosphorous fertilizer rates, except 50% flowering and fruit setting. The combined application of 480 kg ha⁻¹ N and 80 kg ha⁻¹ P fertilizers recorded the highest number of fruit per cluster (5.3), fruit set percentage (81), marketable yield (87.2 t ha⁻¹), total yield (90.2 t ha⁻¹), fruit firmness (13.2) and total soluble solid (4.4) of tomato. The same treatment combination also recorded the lowest percentage of unmarketable yield (3.2%). Plants without any fertilizer application (control treatment) were inferior in all the tested parameters of tomatoes. According to the present study results, farmers at Koga Irrigation Scheme and areas with similar agro-ecology could use the combined application of 480 kg ha⁻¹ N and 80 kg ha⁻¹ P fertilizers for the high tunnel production of tomatoes. As it is a single year result, it is also recommended to repeat the study for the second year.

Keywords: Fruit yield, Fruit firmness, Nutrient management, Soil fertility

Influence of Planting Date and Number of Vine on Growth, Yield and Quality of Watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus* L) at Koga Irrigation Scheme, West Gojjam Zone, Ethiopia **Yibeltal Tilahun^{1,2*}, Melkamu Alemayehu², Enyew Adgo²**

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Abstract

Koga Irrigation Scheme is one of the potential watermelon producing areas in Ethiopia. However, the average yield of watermelon is low due to inappropriate sowing date and poor agronomic practice like vine pruning. Therefore, a field experiment was carried out during the 2021/22 irrigation season to evaluate the influence of sowing date and number of vines on growth, yield and quality of watermelon at Koga Irrigation Scheme, North Mecha Woreda, West Gojjam Zone. The experiment consisted of three sowing dates (D₁: November 12, D₂: December 12 and D₃: January 12) and four level of vine per plant (VP₁: without pruning, VP₂: 2 vines, VP₃: 3 vines, and VP₄: 4 vines arranged with factorial combination in Random Complete Block Design with three replications. Data on phenology, growth, yield and physico-chemical quality attributes were collected and analysed using Statistical Analysis Software (SAS) version 9.4. The results showed that 50% flowering, maturity, number of lateral branches per vine, leaf area, vine length, fruit size classification, fruits per vine and per plant, marketable, unmarketable and total fruit yields, and total soluble solids were influenced by date of sowing and number of vines per plant. The interaction effect of sowing date and number of vine also impacted number of lateral branch per vine, number of fruit per plant, unmarketable yield and, fruit size category. Moreover, significantly highest marketable fruit yield of watermelon was obtained from plants sown on January and from plants with three vines per plant with the values of 45.7 t ha⁻¹) and 42.15 t ha⁻¹, respectively. Based on the partial budget analysis, watermelon sown on January combined with three vines gave the highest net benefit (1,121,616.00 Birr ha⁻¹) and marginal rate of returns (1,944%). Generally, farmers at Koga Irrigation Scheme and at areas with similar agro-ecology should sow watermelon on January and maintain three vines per plants to enhance the productivity and quality of watermelon. As the study is limited to one season and location, further investigation over seasons and locations is also recommended.

Keywords: Crimson Sweet variety, fruit quality, sowing date, vine pruning

Indigenous Knowledge and Perception of Farmers on the Importance of Bitter White Lupine (*Lupinus albus* L.) for Soil Health Improvement and Regenerative Agriculture: Amhara Region, Ethiopia, in Focus.

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Abstract

Smallholder subsistence farmers in the Amhara Region have long relied on cultivation of the orphan crop bitter white lupine (BWL). This study aimed to assess the indigenous knowledge and experiences of smallholder subsistence farmers on integration of BWL into their farming systems for soil health improvement and regenerative agriculture. The data were collected from three administrative zones in which representative districts were selected based on their potential for BWL production. Specifically, 180 households were involved. The data were collected using open-ended questionnaire, Focus Group Discussion (FGD) and in-depth interviews (to key informants.) The quantitative data were analyzed using IBM SPSS version 20 software and the qualitative data were analyzed thematically. The results indicated that on average, farmers allocated about 0.16 ha (12.33%) of their own land to BWL cultivation annually. Farmers perceived BWL as an effective crop for improving soil health, particularly in acidic and marginal lands. They integrated BWL into their farming systems through intercropping, sole crop in rotation, and relay cropping practices. The result also highlighted the potential of BWL for soil health improvement and regenerative agriculture. Furthermore, the findings tended to underscore the multifunctional nature of BWL that contributes to food and nutrition security, soil fertility management, and income generation for smallholder subsistence farmers. Based on the results, it could be recommended that agricultural extension agents and researchers should collaborate with farmers to promote the integration of BWL into farming systems through training and technical support on intercropping, crop rotation and relay cropping practices. Policymakers are also expected to encourage promotion of BWL cultivation as an alternative source for improving soil fertility, particularly in acidic soils and areas where chemical fertilizers are scarce and expensive. Additionally, further research is needed to explore the potential of BWL for sustainable agriculture and soil health improvement in other regions of Ethiopia and beyond.

Keywords: Bitter white lupine, Farming systems, Indigenous knowledge, Regenerative agriculture, Soil health

Exploring the Bitter White Lupine (*Lupinus albus* L.) Nodule and Rhizosphere Soil Bacterial Community Composition

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Abstract

Bitter White Lupine (BWL), *Lupinus albus* L., is a hopeful crop for regenerating infertile land and enhancing soil health, making it a valuable component in sustainable farming systems. This study investigated the microbial communities associated with the BWL root nodules, BWL rhizosphere soil and the rhizosphere of neighboring wheat fields. Data were collected from 36 rhizosphere soil samples and root nodules on 54 BWL plants in six sites. DNA was extracted using the NucleoSpin Soil DNA Isolation Kit, and the 16S rRNA genes were amplified by PCR using specific primers of Illum_341F and Illum_785R. Amplicon sequencing was performed on the Illumina MiSeq platform, and the sequences were processed using Cutadapt software and analyzed using the DADA2 pipeline in R programming. The results revealed significant differences ($P < 0.01$) in microbial composition and diversity on Nodule, BWL rhizosphere soil, and wheat rhizosphere soil. The results also indicated the presence of substantial and unique bacterial communities in the BWL nodule, BWL rhizosphere soil, and wheat rhizosphere soil, with 1957, 8486, and 11186 OTUs (operational taxonomic units), respectively. The Nodule and BWL rhizosphere soil shared 112 OTUs, while the nodule and wheat rhizosphere soil shared 53 OTUs. There were overlaps in the microbial composition between the BWL rhizosphere soil and wheat rhizosphere soil (4845 OTUs), although the OTUs common to all three sample types were relatively small (183 OTUs). The alpha diversity index (Shannon and Simpson Index) revealed the presence of a high diversity of bacterial communities within the rhizosphere soils and, low bacterial diversity within nodules. BWL nodules harbored unique bacterial communities, including nitrogen-fixing rhizobia (*Bradyrhizobium*) and other beneficial microbes. Correlation analyses indicated that soil properties such as available phosphorus, pH, organic carbon, total nitrogen, and soil health index had a weak to moderate positive correlation with the microbial diversity and composition in the nodule and rhizosphere soils. The findings of this study could provide valuable insights into the potential role of the BWL nodule and rhizosphere microbiome in promoting soil health and fertility. Future studies should focus on functional analyses of these microbial communities to further elucidate their contributions to soil health and crop productivity.

Keywords: Microbial diversity, Nitrogen fixation, Nodule, Soil health

Phenotypic Characterization of Rhizobia and Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Fungi on Common Bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) Plant

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Abstract

Nitrogen and phosphorous are essential elements for plant growth and development which are supplied by mutual symbiosis of rhizobia and arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF) in cultivated legume plants. This work aimed at isolation and characterization of rhizobia and AMF from rhizosphere soils of common bean collected from major growing areas (Adama, Meki, Alemtena and Melkassa) of Easter Ethiopia. A total of 21 rhizobium isolates, 8 genera and 29 morph species of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi were identified. All of the rhizobium isolates were subjected to gram staining, and microscopic observation showed that all are gram negative rods. The isolates varied in morphology, i.e. 33% formed small colonies (<2 mm), whereas the majority of the isolates (67%) had intermediate colony size, i.e. had diameters >2 mm. Almost all isolates did not absorb Congo red implying that they could be rhizobia. While further confirming these isolates, out of 21 isolates, all isolates showed no growth/little growth on the glucose peptone medium indicating character of rhizobia as a conventional rule. The acid base production test has also showed 13 isolates showed acidic reaction on YEMA-BTB as having yellow color around the colony indicating that these isolates were fast grower while 8 isolates showed blue color indicating that they were slow growers. They were found to be moderately sensitive to salt (up to 2%), temperature (40%) and pH (5-8). The result indicated that inoculation of plants with rhizobium isolates had impact on shoot dry weight, nodule number and nodule dry weight. Of the isolated rhizobium 14 isolates had 50-80% effectiveness while 8 isolates showed high effectiveness (>80%). A total of 29 AMF morphospecies, belonging to Eight genera (Acaulospora, Ambispora, Glomus, Entrophosphora, Funneliformis, Septoglomus, Rhizophagus, and Gigaspora), were identified in the rhizospheres of common bean plant. Twelve species belonged to Acaulospora, 2 each to Funneliformis and Gigaspora, 9 to Glomus, 1 each to Rhizophagus, Entrophosphora and Ambispora. Spores of two genera Acaulospora (*Ac. Capsicula* and *Ac. Sporocarpia*) and Glomus (*Gl. Constrictum*) had higher spore production, accounting for 50%, 50%, 100% isolation frequency and 1.50, 1.50 and 3.75 abundance of the total number of spores under the study areas respectively. Spore density and total root colonization were higher at the study areas of Adama while diversity was higher at Melkassa. Hence, all isolates confirmed as ineffective and could be considered as plant growth promoting microbial strains.

Key words: Abundance, Effectiveness, Isolate, Morphology

Effects of Rhizobia Strains, Lime and Starter Nitrogen on Soil Fertility and Yields of Faba Bean (*Vicia fabae* L.) in Acidic Soils of North Micha District, Northwestern Ethiopia.

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Abstract

Soil acidity is one of the major soil chemical constraints which limit agricultural productivity in North-western Ethiopia. The study was conducted to evaluate the influence of lime, rhizobia strains and starter nitrogen fertilizer on yield and yield attributes of faba bean in acid soil at North Micha district, North western Ethiopia. A total of 18 treatments including three rhizobia strains (0, FB-37 and FB-1035), three levels of starter nitrogen (0, 10 and 20 kg/ha) and two levels of lime (0 and 2 t/ha) were tested in factorial RCBD design. Sole application of lime, rhizobia strains as well as starter nitrogen, individually produced grain yield of 467 kg/ha, 216 kg/ha, 150 kg/ha more than the control respectively. However, the maximum seed yield was recorded from the combined application of rhizobia strains, lime and starter nitrogen. Significantly ($P < 0.001$) higher plant height (104.1cm), number of pod per plant (18.4), number of seed per plant (41.6), above ground biomass yield (6.122 t/ha) and grain yield (2.87 t/ha) was obtained from the combined application of FB-1035 +2 t/ha lime+10 kg/ha N. While significant increases ($P < 0.001$) in nodule number, effective nodule number and nodule dry weight were obtained due to application of FB-1035 + 2 t/ha lime + 20 kg/ha N in par with Fb-1035 +2 t/ha lime + 10 kg/ha N. The combined use of Fb-1035 +2 t/ha lime + 10 kg/ha N, producing a maximum net profit of 165,290-birr ha⁻¹ with a superior marginal rate of return 2185. Therefore, this study shows that in terms of both its economic feasibility and maximum grain yield advantage, was obtained from combined application of FB-1035 + 2 t/ha lime + 10 kg/ha N.

Keywords: soil acidity, Faba bean, Rhizobium inoculation, lime, starter Nitrogen

Food System Lab Bahir Dar

Effects of Rhizobia Strains, Lime and Starter Nitrogen on Soil Fertility and Yields of Faba bean (*Vicia fabae L.*) in Acidic Soils of Banja District, Northwestern Ethiopia

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Abstract

Soil acidity is one of the major soil chemical constraints which limit agricultural productivity in North-western Ethiopia. The study was conducted to examine the influence of lime, rhizobia strains and starter nitrogen fertilizer on yield and yield attributes of faba bean in acid soil at Banja district of Awi Zone, Northwestern Ethiopia. A total of 18 treatments namely three rhizobia strains (0, FB-37 and FB-1035), three levels of starter nitrogen (0, 10 and 20 kg/ha) and two levels of lime (0 and 2 t/ha) were tested in factorial RCBD design. The results revealed that the combined application of rhizobia strain, lime, starter nitrogen significantly impacted ($p < 0.001$) on nodule number, biomass yield and grain yield of faba bean. Maximum grain yield (3.38 t/ha and 3.15 t/ha) and above ground biomass yield (8.5 t/ha and 8.27 t/ha) were recorded on the application of FB-37 + 2t/ha lime + 10 kg/ha N and FB-1035 + 2 t/ha lime + 10kg/ha N respectively. Generally, this study results showed that maximum grain yield advantage could be obtained from combined application of rhizobia strains, lime and starter nitrogen.

Keywords: Biomass yield, Grain yield, Rhizobium inoculation, Soil acidity

Effects of Inoculation, Acidic Soil Amendment Using Lime, and Starter Nitrogen on Soil Health and *Faba bean* Production at Koga Irrigation Scheme, in Mecha District, west North-western Ethiopia

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Abstract

Soil acidity is one of several factors affecting nutrient deficiencies and toxicities, low activities of beneficial microorganisms, and reduced plant root growth, which limits absorption of nutrients and water. Therefore, adjustment and maintenance of soil acidity using different mechanisms has become an essential management of acidic soils to increase crop production. A field experiment was conducted to see effects of inoculation, acidic soil amendment using lime, and starter nitrogen application on soil health, and Faba bean (*Vicia faba* L.) P

Production at Koga Irrigation Scheme, North-western, Ethiopia. The three factors such as lime rates (0, and 2 t ha⁻¹), starter Nitrogen (0, 10 and 20kg·ha⁻¹), and rhizobium inoculation (0, strain1 and strain2) were combined in 2x3x3 factorial arrangement of RCBD in three replications. The data were collected on soil health parameters, yield and yield components of Faba bean and subjected to the analysis of variance (ANOVA). The ANOVA results revealed that plant height, number of pods per plant, number of seeds per pod, hundred seeds weight, above ground biomass, and grain yield were significantly affected by the treatment. Soil p^H, Bulk density, and total porosity were also affected by the treatment. Therefore, the highest Faba bean yield was obtained from the application of 2t limes ha⁻¹, starter Nitrogen 20kg·ha⁻¹, and Rhizobium strain2. Therefore, the integrated application of the aforementioned rates of lime, starter Nitrogen, and rhizobium inoculation could be recommended for maximizing the productivity and profitability of Faba bean in the study area and beyond with similar agro-ecologies.

Keywords: Inoculation, Acidic Soil, Starter Nitrogen, Soil Health

Effects of Bitter White Lupine Green Manure, Vermicompost, and Chemical Fertilizers on Soil Health and Wheat Productivity

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Abstract

Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) is a significant cereal crop that belongs to the Poacea family, and it is highly valued globally based on its cultivated area or yield. In the majority of Ethiopia's highlands, the crop's yield and production are severely hampered by acidity of the soil. Ethiopia's farming system is severely affected by soil deterioration. The objectives of this research are, therefore, to assess the relative effects of vermicompost, chemical fertilizer, and green manure (from bitter lupines) on soil health; investigate the productivity of wheat crops in response to applications of chemical, vermicompost, and green manure from bitter lupines; and to identify and recommend the ideal amount of bitter lupine biomass for green manuring in wheat production systems. The study was carried out at the Ambo Mesk site of the Koga Irrigation scheme. Three levels of chemical fertilizers (0, 50% of the recommendation, and full recommendation), three levels of fresh biomass (0, 2.5, and 5 t/ha dry mater based) and three levels of vermicompost (0, 2.5 and 5 t/ha) were the treatments included in the experiment. Ten randomly chosen plants from the net plot area were used to collect all agronomic data on the phenological, vegetative growth, and yield-related aspects of wheat crops. Each treatment plot had composite post-harvest soil samples taken, and the soil laboratory's operating manuals and protocols were followed in the analysis of the samples' properties. The results showed grain yield of wheat was significantly increased following different rates of vermicompost, lupine green manure and inorganic fertilizer. The integrated use of lupine green manure and vermicompost along with mineral fertilizer also found improved important soil properties and wheat production.

Key words: Chemical fertilizer, Lupine green manure, Soil health, Vermicompost, wheat productivity

Effects of Bitter White Lupine Green Manure, Vermicompost, and Chemical Fertilizers on Soil Health and Wheat Productivity

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Abstract

Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) is a significant cereal crop that belongs to the Poacea family, and it is highly valued globally based on its cultivated area or yield. In the majority of Ethiopia's highlands, the crop's yield and production are severely hampered by acidity of the soil. Ethiopia's farming system is severely affected by soil deterioration. The objectives of this research are, therefore, to assess the relative effects of vermicompost, chemical fertilizer, and green manure (from bitter lupines) on soil health; investigate the productivity of wheat crops in response to applications of chemical, vermicompost, and green manure from bitter lupines; and to identify and recommend the ideal amount of bitter lupine biomass for green manuring in wheat production systems. The study was carried out at the Ambo Mesk site of the Koga Irrigation scheme. Three levels of chemical fertilizers (0, 50% of the recommendation, and full recommendation), three levels of fresh biomass (0, 2.5, and 5 t/ha dry mater based) and three levels of vermicompost (0, 2.5 and 5 t/ha) were the treatments included in the experiment. Ten randomly chosen plants from the net plot area were used to collect all agronomic data on the phenological, vegetative growth, and yield-related aspects of wheat crops. Each treatment plot had composite post-harvest soil samples taken, and the soil laboratory's operating manuals and protocols were followed in the analysis of the samples' properties. The results showed grain yield of wheat was significantly increased following different rates of vermicompost, lupine green manure and inorganic fertilizer. The integrated use of lupine green manure and vermicompost along with mineral fertilizer also found improved important soil properties and wheat production.

Key words: Chemical fertilizer, Lupine green manure, Soil health, Vermicompost, wheat productivity

Effect of Inoculation, Lime, and Starter Nitrogen on Soil Properties and Crop Yield of Haricot Bean in Northwestern Ethiopia

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ABSTRACT

Poor soil fertility management and inappropriate agronomic packages are a major crop production constraint, in Ethiopia, particularly affecting the haricot bean yield, which remains below its potential. Hence, the current study was conducted to see effects of lime, starter nitrogen and rhizobia on soil properties, biological nitrogen fixation and Yield of haricot bean in Koga Irrigation scheme, located northwestern Ethiopia. Treatments consisted of two rates of lime (0 and 2 t ha⁻¹), three rates of nitrogen (0, 10 and 20 kg ha⁻¹), and three rhizobia strains (0, HAMBI3570 and HAMBI3562) with a test crop of SER-119 haricot bean variety in factorial combinations were laid out in randomized complete block design with three replications during two rainfed (2021-2022) cropping seasons. *The collected data were analyzed by SAS version 9.4.* The results of the study showed that combined application of lime, starter nitrogen and rhizobia application increased significantly total porosity by 9.05%, soil pH 0.96 units, organic carbon 0.88%, total nitrogen 0.046%, CEC 14.91 cmol (+) kg⁻¹), and available P by 22.86 ppm and decreased bulk density by 0.24g/cm³ compared to the control (P<0.05). Similarly, the interaction effects of lime, starter nitrogen and rhizobia application significantly increased plant height, total number of nodules, effective number of nodules, number of pods per plant, number of seed per pod and grain yield (p<0.01). Furthermore, combined application of 2 t ha⁻¹ limes, 20 kg ha⁻¹ starter nitrogen, HAMBI3570 rhizobia strain had the highest grain yield (4681.80 kg ha⁻¹), whereas the control treatment yielded the lowest grain output of 766.74 kg ha⁻¹. In conclusion, the combined application of lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobia could enhance soil physicochemical properties and crop yields, and is recommended for adapting in the study area and beyond where there are similar soil fertility management challenges

Key words: Haricot bean, lime, Bio fertilizer, rhizobia, root nodulation, starter nitrogen, soil fertility, Acid soils

Growth performance of Male Monosex Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) using Hapa Culture at Koga Reservoir, Merawi, Ethiopia

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Abstract

Mixed sex Nile tilapia in pond culture system usually results in frequent spawning, varied sizes and stunted growth that has no much advantage to fish farmers. Hence, an experimental study using hapa culture technology was conducted in the main reservoir at Koga Irrigation scheme, located around Bahir Dar city, on monosex fingerling tilapia. The male fingerlings as a quality fish seed identified manually and stocked inside the hapa aiming to evaluate mainly the growth performance and survival rate of the male monosex tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*). The length-weight relationship, condition factor and some important physicochemical water quality parameters were also considered. Initial body weight and length of the fishes were 61.42 ± 27.30 g and 15.20 ± 2.11 cm respectively. Thirty fishes were randomly sampled to measure their individual weight and length on weekly basis for three months (from February to April 2022). The average body weight gain and length of fishes became 81.71 ± 29.51 g and 16.85 ± 2.82 cm respectively and the difference was statistically significant. Particularly, at the end of the experiment, the specific growth rate attained for each fish per day was 0.76%. The mean condition factor of the reservoir was 1.67 ± 0.30 , which indicated within the standard set for healthy fish condition. Water temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen and Secchi depth measurement of the hapa were within the optimum ranges for the growth of Nile tilapia, whereas conductivity was not within the optimum range but within acceptable range for fish growth. In conclusion, the male mono-sexed Nile tilapia examined were in good condition and healthy attending very good growth performance and can be cultured in large scale. Therefore, this type of fish production system should be scaled up by developing aquaculture in the locality as well as in other ecological setups.

Key Words: Hapa culture, Koga reservoir, length, Mono sex, *Oreochromis niloticus*, weight

Status of Integrated Fish Farming Practices in Ethiopia. A review article

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Abstract

Integrated fish farming is an innovative and sustainable agricultural practice by combining aquaculture and other forms of agriculture to create a synergistic system that enhances productivity, environmental sustainability, and economic benefits. This review focuses on analyzing the development, implementation, and impact of integrated fish farming practices in Ethiopia. The country has a diverse agro-ecological zones and significant water resources which provide considerable potential for expansion of integrated fish farming. Integrated fish farming particularly involves the integration of fish farming with livestock, poultry, and crop production. This approach optimizes the use of resources by recycling waste from one component to be used as an input for another in which overall farming efficiency is maintained. The integrated rice-fish farming in Fogera district at South Gondar zone is a good example for this. The major results for the stated integrated farming tend to prove the success of practicing an integrated farming system in Ethiopia for increased agricultural productivity, improved food security, and enhanced livelihoods for smallholder farmers. Particularly, in the integrated fish farming, the nutrient-rich fishpond water is used for irrigating crops, which in turn improves soil fertility and crop yields. The livestock and poultry droppings are used for fish feed which reduces the cost of inputs. The integrated farming also helps in the effective management of farm resources that results in reduced environmental impact and increased biodiversity. However, the adaptation of integrated fish farming in Ethiopia faces several challenges. These include limited access to quality fish fingerlings, inadequate technical knowledge among farmers, insufficient financial support, and lack of effective policy frameworks. Addressing these challenges requires concerted efforts from governmental and non-governmental organizations and research institutions. Particularly, these institutions could provide training, improve infrastructure, and develop supportive policies. In conclusion, integrated fish farming could be a viable solution to enhance agricultural productivity and sustainability in Ethiopia. That is, by addressing the existing challenges the integrated fish farming can significantly contribute to the economic development and food security of Ethiopia. Further research and investment are essential to optimize these systems and promote widespread adaptation of other farmers.

Keywords: Fish, livestock, small holder farmers, synergy, vegetable

Proximate composition of local available ingredients for fish feed in West Gojam Zone, Ethiopia

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The proximate composition of local ingredients in potential feedstuffs for Nile tilapia fish feed formulation is not recognized among different farming stakeholders, which is cost-effective compared to artificial fish feed made by the company in Ethiopia, particularly in the Amhara region. This study was conducted to identify and investigate the proximate analysis of locally available ingredients in the West Gojam zone for Nile tilapia fish feed. Proximate analyses in the formulated feeds were determined using standard procedures and methods by adopting the association of official methods of chemical analysis from 2005 at the Poly Food Analysis and Chemistry Lab, Bahir Dar University. In this study, crude protein (CP), lipid, moisture, ash, and dry matter content of haricot bean, fish meal, bone meal, blood meal, pumpkin, tree lucerne, soybean, and wheat bran were analyzed and determined. Data were analyzed using a one-way ANOVA to compare means in the nutrient contents of the ingredients. The quantity of crude protein in different samples of ingredients ranged from 8.00 to 58.53%. The maximum amount of CP content (58.53%) was recorded in the fish meal, followed by bone and blood meal, and then haricot bean. Pumpkin and tree lucerne were recorded at 30% and 23.70%, respectively. The minimum amount of CP (8.00%) was recorded in wheat bran. Statistically, the CP content among these ingredients varied significantly (<0.01). The content of fat in different feeds ranged from 2.08 to 17.40%. The highest value (17.40%) of fat content was found in bone and blood meal, followed by soybean meal (14.55%), and the minimum (2.08%) was recorded in haricot bean. Statistically, the fat content among these ingredients was insignificant (>0.05). Dry matters were recorded at 90.50, 94.20, 91.05, 93.34, 89.20, 93.03, and 94.60% in fish meal, bone and blood meal, haricot bean, soybean, pumpkin, tree lucerne, and wheat bran, respectively, and statistically varied insignificantly (>0.05). Moreover, the values of moisture and ash were recorded at 9.50, 5.80, 8.95, 6.66, 10.80, 8.24, 5.40, and 22.26, 26.00, 4.06, 5.12, 6.35, 6.64, and 3.05%, respectively, in the order of fish meal, bone and blood meal, haricot bean, soybean, pumpkin, tree lucerne, and wheat bran, with an insignificant difference (>0.05). The highest value of moisture (10.80%) was recorded in the pumpkin, and the lowest value of moisture (5.40%) was recorded in wheat bran. The highest amount of ash (26.00%) was also found in bone and blood meal, and the lowest amount of ash (3.05%) was found in wheat bran. This feed was formulated and analyzed for fish categorized into four diets to evaluate the growth performance of the cultured fish. To maintain the optimum nutrient content for the requirement of rapid body growth in fish farms, *fish farmers should consider the proper analysis for measuring the nutrients in the feed.*

Key words: Proximate analysis, crude proteins, fat, dry matter, feed formulation, fish

Micronutrient Inadequacy of Lactating Mothers in Rural Areas of North Mecha District, Amhara Region, Ethiopia

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Abstract

Lactating mothers are frequently at risk for nutritional deficiencies due to physiological requirements of lactation. Throughout the world, a significant number of lactating mothers have micronutrient intake inadequacy. However, evidence on micronutrient intake inadequacy during lactation is limited in rural Ethiopia. Therefore, this study aimed to identify micronutrient intake inadequacy and associated factors of lactating mothers. A community-based cross-sectional study was conducted, on lactating mothers in rural areas of North Mecha district of Amhara Region, Northwest Ethiopia from February 1 to 18, 2023. A multistage sampling technique was used to select 449 participants. An interviewer-administered questionnaire was employed to collect dietary intake data by using a single multiphasic interactive 24-hour dietary recall. The NutriSurvey 2007 software and Ethiopia, Tanzania, and Kenya food composition tables were used to calculate nutrient values for the selected 12 micronutrients. A logistic regression analysis was conducted to determine the factors contributing to the overall micronutrient intake inadequacy, and statistical significance was determined at a p-value <0.05. The results showed that the overall prevalence of micronutrient intake inadequacy was 72.3% (95% CI: 67.9, 76.5). The odds of micronutrient intake inadequacy were 2.5 times higher among lactating mothers aged 18–25 years old as compared to mothers in the age group ≥36 years old (AOR = 2.52, 95% CI: 1.09, 5.83). Mothers with an educational status of unable to read and write and primary school incomplete were 3.5 (AOR = 3.49, 95% CI: 1.24, 9.83) and 3.6 (AOR = 3.56, 95% CI: 1.06, 11.99) times more likely to have micronutrient intake inadequacy than mothers with secondary school completed or above educational status, respectively. Mothers whose partner's occupation was other than farming were 3.3 times more likely to have micronutrient intake inadequacy as compared to mothers whose partners were engaged in farming (AOR = 3.32, 95% CI: 1.08, 10.27). Lactating mothers who were from food-insecure households were 83% more likely to have high micronutrient intake inadequacy as compared to lactating mothers from food secure households (AOR = 1.83, 95% CI: 1.04, 3.23). Lactating mothers with nutrition-related unfavourable attitudes were 77% more likely to have inadequate intake of micronutrients compared to lactating mothers with favourable attitudes (AOR = 1.77, 95% CI: 1.07, 2.93). In conclusion, the prevalence of micronutrient intake inadequacy among lactating mothers was high. The age of the mothers, educational status of the mothers, occupation of the partner, household food security, and nutrition-related attitude were significantly associated with

m micronutrient intake inadequacy. Therefore, community-driven nutrition education and interventions could be needed to address the high micronutrient intake inadequacy among lactating mothers in rural Ethiopia.

Keywords: Dietary intake, Nutrient inadequacy, Lactating mothers, North Mecha, Amhara, Northwest Ethiopia

Micronutrient Intake Inadequacies in Northwest Ethiopian Children Aged 6–23 Months

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Abstract

The early stages of childhood are a crucial period of life for health, with inadequate nutrition impacting physical growth, cognitive development, and the immune system. A considerable proportion of children are affected by micronutrient intake inadequacy and deficiency across the globe. Evidence on micronutrient intake among children aged 6–23 months is limited in northwest Ethiopia, where there is a divergence between production and dietary consumption practices compared to other regions of the country. This study aimed to investigate micronutrient inadequacy and associated factors among children aged 6–23 months.

A community-based cross-sectional study was conducted taking 435 children aged 6–23 months in the North Mecha District of Amhara Region, Northwest Ethiopia, from February 1 to 18, 2023. The study participants were selected using a multistage sampling technique. A multiphasic interactive 24-hour dietary recall was used to collect dietary intake data via an interviewer-administered questionnaire. Nutrient values for the selected 12 micronutrients were calculated using the NutriSurvey 2007 software and food composition tables from Ethiopia, Tanzania, and Kenya. SPSS version 25 was used for the remaining parts of the analysis. The Nutrient Adequacy Ratio (NAR) and Mean Adequacy Ratio (MAR) were calculated to evaluate the nutrient intakes. To identify the factors associated with overall micronutrient intake inadequacy, a multivariable binary logistic regression analysis was performed, with statistical significance determined at a p -value < 0.05 . The results indicated that the overall prevalence of micronutrient intake inadequacy was 64.7% (95% CI: 59.9, 69.2). The odds of micronutrient intake inadequacy were 2.8 times higher for children aged 6–8 months as compared to children aged 9–23 months (AOR = 2.80, 95% CI: 1.71, 4.59). Children with paternal education of unable to read and write and able to read and write were 3.1 (AOR = 3.12, 95% CI: 1.26, 7.70) and 2.4 (AOR = 2.40, 95% CI: 1.01, 5.73) times more likely to have micronutrient intake inadequacy, respectively, compared to children with paternal education of primary school completed and above. The likelihood of micronutrient intake inadequacy was 1.8 times higher for children with mothers who had an unfavourable nutrition-related attitude than those children of mothers who had a favourable attitude (AOR = 1.76, 95% CI: 1.02, 3.05).

In conclusion, inadequate intake of micronutrients was shown to be highly prevalent on children aged 6–23 months. Child age, paternal education, and maternal nutrition-related attitude were

significantly associated with micronutrient intake inadequacy. Therefore, integrating community-guided nutrition interventions targeting nutrition-related knowledge and attitudes of parents is critical in addressing the inadequate micronutrient intake of children in the study community, where production is not a problem.

Keywords: Dietary intake, Nutrient inadequacy, young children, North Mecha, Northwest Ethiopia

Validation of the Minimum Dietary Diversity for Women as a Predictor of Micronutrient Adequacy of Lactating Women in Ethiopia

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Abstract

The Minimum Dietary Diversity for Women (MDD-W) indicator is used as a proxy indicator for assessing micronutrient adequacy among women of the reproductive age group. Variations were observed in studies, and there was also a lack of evidence on performance of this proxy indicator in Ethiopia, a country with diverse dietary consumption practices. This study aimed to validate the performance of the MDD-W in predicting micronutrient intake adequacy on lactating women. A community-based cross-sectional study was conducted on randomly selected 457 lactating women in Northwest Ethiopia from February 2 to 18, 2023. A multistage sampling technique was used to select the participants. A single multiphasic interactive 24-hour dietary recall was used to collect dietary intake data. Ten food groups were used to compute the Minimum Dietary Diversity for Women, and the Mean Adequacy Ratio was used to assess nutrient intake adequacy. Spearman's rank correlation test, Cohen's kappa statistics, and ROC curve analysis were conducted. The optimal cutoff points for Minimum Dietary Diversity for Women were determined by selecting the points that maximized the Youden index. The results showed that MDD-W had a statistically significant poor positive correlation ($\rho=0.19$, $p<0.001$) and poor predictive ability (AUC=0.62, 95% CI: 0.56, 0.67; $p<0.001$) with the Mean Adequacy Ratio of determining micronutrient intake adequacy. The sensitivity and specificity of the MDD-W in the ≥ 5 food groups were 25.2% and 82.3%, respectively. The optimal cutoff point for MDD-W to predict micronutrient intake adequacy was ≥ 3 food groups.

In conclusion, Minimum Dietary Diversity for Women had a poor correlation and poor predictive ability in predicting micronutrient intake adequacy. The variations noted in studies and differences from the Food and Agriculture Organization recommendations regarding the cutoff and level of performance of MDD-W in defining micronutrient adequacy warrant further investigation.

Keywords: Minimum Dietary Diversity, Nutrient Adequacy, Validation, Lactating Women, Ethiopia

Minimum Dietary Diversity as a predictor of micronutrient adequacy for children aged 6-23 months in Ethiopia: Validation of the proxy indicator

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Abstract

The Minimum Dietary Diversity is a proxy indicator of micronutrient adequacy for children aged 6–23 months. There is a lack of evidence on performance of this proxy indicator in Ethiopia, a country with diverse dietary habits. Therefore, this study aimed to validate the performance of the Minimum Dietary Diversity to predict micronutrient adequacy against the Mean Adequacy Ratio among children aged 6–23 months in the North Mecha District, Northwest Ethiopia.

A community-based cross-sectional study of 457 randomly selected participants was conducted from February 2 to 18, 2023. A single multiphasic interactive 24-hour dietary recall was used to collect dietary intake data. Spearman's rank correlation test, Cohen's kappa statistics, and Receiver Operating Curve analysis were conducted. The optimal cutoff point for Minimum Dietary Diversity for children aged 6–23 months was determined by selecting the points that maximized the Youden index. Statistical significance was determined with a p-value < 0.05 using a 95% confidence interval.

The results revealed that the Minimum Dietary Diversity for Children aged 6–23 months had a statistically significant, moderate positive correlation ($\rho = 0.62$, $p < 0.001$) and a fair predictive ability (AUC = 0.78, 95% CI: 0.74, 0.83, $p < 0.001$) with the Mean Adequacy Ratio to predict the adequate intake of micronutrients accurately. The Minimum Dietary Diversity score (≥ 5 food groups) had a sensitivity of 22.4% and a specificity of 91.4%, denoting slight agreement. The optimal cutoff point for Minimum Dietary Diversity to predict micronutrient intake adequacy was found to be ≥ 3 food groups, with a sensitivity of 85.5% and a specificity of 62.9%. This optimal cutoff adjustment improved the agreement between the Minimum Dietary Diversity indicator and micronutrient intake adequacy to a moderate level.

In conclusion, the minimum dietary diversity for children aged 6–23 months had a statistically significant, moderate positive correlation, and a fair predictive ability with the Mean Adequacy Ratio to predict micronutrient intake adequacy accurately. This study result highlights the need for further research to evaluate the effectiveness of the new minimum dietary diversity indicator as a proxy indicator at the defined cutoff for determining micronutrient adequacy in diverse populations.

Keywords: Minimum Dietary Diversity, Nutrient Adequacy, Validation, Children, Ethiopia

Diagnostic performance of Mid-Upper Arm Circumference (MUAC) and Mid-Upper Arm Circumference-for-Age z-score (MUACZ) in screening acute malnutrition on children aged 6-23 months in Amhara Region, Ethiopia

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Abstract

Mid-Upper Arm Circumference (MUAC), Mid-Upper Arm Circumference-for-Age z-score (MUACZ), or Weight-for-Length Z-Score (WHZ) are used to screen for acute malnutrition (wasting) in children. Studies conducted in various countries have indicated variability in the agreement between these assessments at the standard cutoffs. Therefore, this study aimed to validate the diagnostic performance of MUAC and MUACZ in screening for wasting among children aged 6-23 months in Ethiopia.

A community-based cross-sectional study was conducted on 457 randomly selected children aged 6-23 months from February 2-18, 2023. The Spearman's rank correlation test, Cohen's kappa statistics, and Receiver Operating Curve analysis were conducted. The optimal cutoff points for MUAC and MUACZ were determined by selecting the points that maximized the Youden index.

The MUAC, MUACZ, and WHZ results revealed that the percentage of misclassification in screening wasting was approximately 16%. MUAC and MUACZ had low sensitivity but high specificity and showed poor correlation and poor predictive ability with WHZ when screening subjects for acute malnutrition using the standard cutoffs. The optimal cutoff for MUAC and MUACZ to define global acute malnutrition at WHZ < -2 SD was 13.6cm and -0.43 SD, respectively. In addition, the optimal cutoffs for diagnosing Severe Acute Malnutrition in children with WHZ of < -3 SD were found to be 13.1 cm and -1.91 SD for MUAC and MUACZ, respectively. The optimal cutoff values also vary in sex and age categories.

In conclusion, Both MUAC and MUACZ had poor performance in screening acute malnutrition and a significant proportion of children were missed despite they were wasted as compared to WHZ at the standard cutoffs. This may affect admission and discharge rates and significantly impact children's health. To ensure the quality of acute malnutrition screening and treatment services, modifications in the standard cutoffs are needed.

Keywords: Acute malnutrition, Wasting, MUAC, MUACZ, WHZ, Validation, Children, Amhara, Ethiopia

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